

condatis

Condatis Case Study: Scenarios for restoration of degraded tropical forest in a 'corridor' between Mount Halimun and Mount Salak, in West Java

NERC

SCIENCE OF THE ENVIRONMENT

UNIVERSITY OF LIVERPOOL

Goal: to use field-based habitat suitability data to demonstrate how restoration could enable movement of threatened species through a human-impacted wildlife corridor in the Mount Halimun Salak National Park (TNGHS), West Java. We hope to support decisions about the effective areas for restoration by comparing the present situation with actually planned and even more optimistic scenarios.

CONDATIS PARAMETERS

Mount Halimun (H) and Mount Salak (S), separated by the wildlife corridor (yellow box), within the National Park (white line).

What kind of species are we interested in?	Javan Gibbon and Javan Leopard (endangered species)
What is our source and target?	Source is Mount Halimun (blue); target is Mount Salak (green)
Why do our species need to move?	For larger total populations, long-term resilience and genetic exchange, perhaps also to avoid isolation as the climate changes.
What constitutes habitat?	Forest, of suitable quality*
What kind of prioritisation are we performing?	Testing and comparing scenarios for restoration of degraded forest
Who will be interested in the results?	Mount Halimun Salak National Park Authorities & associated parties

*Habitat suitability layers provided by Prof Lilik Prasetyo, IPB

SUMMARY CONDATIS RESULTS

Flow maps & colonisation speeds:

A - Javan Gibbon (*Hylobates moloch*); **B** - Javan Leopard (*Panthera pardus melas*)

- The wildlife corridor has greater connectivity for the gibbon compared to the leopard, as illustrated by colonisation speeds
- Each species uses different habitat patches within the landscape, with the leopard restricted to the northern ridge whilst the gibbon moves through many more areas
- There is some overlap (↙) in the habitat patches used by these two species along the northern ridge; this is a particularly critical area to conserve.

Restoration scenarios will have a positive impact on the colonisation speed of the landscape

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